

Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională Argeș

**Personal Development International Conference
1st Edition - Pitești 2022**

**Conferința Internațională Dezvoltare Personală
Ediția I - Pitești 2022**

**Book of abstracts
Volum de rezumate**

Editura Ars Libri

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Ars Libri

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Plenary Opening

Moderator: Mihaela Lungu,

Special Guests:

Phd. Larisa Sadovei – Dean of the Faculty of Education and Informatics, State Pedagogical University „I. Creangă” from Chişinău,

Alina Manea – General Inspector of Argeş County School Inspectorate,

Maria Cătălina Dumitraşcu – Deputy of the General Inspector of Argeş County School Inspectorate,

Angelica Sireţchi – psychoterapist, personal development trainer, Iaşi Institute for Family and Couple,

Costin Dedu – President of Imago Mundi Association, Adrian Apostol – President of SAKURA Association,

Hosts:

Ciucă Emilia Rodica – Headmaster of County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance, Argeş,

Ruse Cătălin – President of AsProEdu Association

Simposium

Projects and funds for development

Session 1

Projects and funds for development – PPS

Moderator: Mihaela Lungu

VOLUNTEER FOR THE PLANETISE

(1) Adrian APOSTOL

(1) President of SAKURA Association, Romania

Source of the Grant: Erasmus + ESC

Purpose of the project is to encourage young people and citizens from local communities in Branesti, Pantelimon, Ciorogarla and Dragomiresti Vale in Ilfov County, but also from the rural area of Turkey, to understand the climate challenges that Europe is currently facing, as well as the whole world. The project wants to involve as many young people as possible in activities to promote and support environmental protection and greening polluted areas. The current project will use as a working tool the Game "Planetise" which has non-formal methods of education to facilitate communication and to help inform young people about climate change.

Objectives: O1. Informing and instructing a number of 200 young people at local, national and European level regarding the selective system of managing waste. O2. The teaching/instruction objective of ESC: The 30 ESC volunteers who are directly involved in the project will be trained along 40 Romanian volunteers from the local communities in Ilfov (Ciorogârla, Dragomirești Vale, Brănești and Pantelimon) to act and do visible actions for the protection of the environment and realize 8 greening campaigns for raising the level of awareness of the youth about the impact the climatic changes have at the global level. O3. EU Climate Neutrality Goal 2050, informing 500 young people and citizens about European climate goals. O4. The objective of capitalizing on the results of the strategic project PLANETISE as a non-formal work instrument, developing it and making it more adequate for ecological projects of the NGOs, as well as support for schools and high schools in ecological education. O5. The strategical development objective: founding an ecological center for informing, in joint effort with the Ilfov County Council.

Impact: The current project plans to have a major impact on local rural EU communities, young people and volunteers they work with and address. We specify that by carrying out the activities of this project we want to concretely make young people aware of how we individually pollute the dish and how we can reduce this by exemplifying young people in practice how we can act. The impact on the direct participants will be reflected in the increase of the conscious and motivated involvement in actions to reduce the pollution, the development of an attitude of social and community activism, the increase of the civic sense and of the level of ecological education.

Keywords: Non formal education, volunteering, climate change.

FIGHTING AGAINST STEREOTYPES, INEQUALITY AND VIOLENCE WITH ART TOOLS IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEMS

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Objectives: The purpose of this paper is to inform about educational tools created to prevent VAW (violence against women). Statistics indicate that Romania, a deep conservative and traditionalist country, although it took steps to promote women rights and gender equality, it is still wavering between supporting policies and the collective mentality that justifies VAW and GBV (gender-based violence). Considering art as an extension of the society's beliefs and an influence factor for future attitudes/stereotypes, the "REGENERART – Rethinking GENDER Equality through ART" project chose to create education tools to deconstruct gender stereotypes and rethink a violence-free society. The didactic visual support worksheets were based on a project created guide and followed the analyze of the dichotomies observed. At least 12 visual support forms like the one above, were created by each partner, regarding art from its country or region (painting, graphic, sculptures, photography) to be included in a future training course. They are meant to develop critical thinking and rethink attitudes.

Coordinator of the project: Fondazione Pangea Onlus, Italy

Source of the Grant: Erasmus +, European Union program

Management details: project number 2020-1- IT02-KA227-SCH-094954, Budget 295.110,00 EUR, 24 months (April 2021-April2023).

Results: e-learning course; online exhibition; Textbook, *Looking at Art from a gender perspective*; Manifesto for a new gender-sensitive art.

Conclusions: Gender equality is a necessary condition to achieve growth and social cohesion and a key element in the prevention of VAW (violence against women).

Keywords: Education, Art tools, VAW, prevention.

**INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS FOR ADULT EDUCATION” - MIPEA
2020-1-RO01-KA104-079477**

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Programme Operator: National Agency for Community Programs in the Field of Vocational Education and Training (ANPCDEFP)

Project Promoter: Liceul Tehnologic Nr.1, Maracineni, Arges, Romania

Source of the Grant: EACEA through Erasmus+ Programme

Partners: Erasmus Learning Academy, Bologna, Italy; Project Management Spain Erasmus Plus, Alicante, Spain; EUROPASS, Florence, Italy.

Objectives: Developing the competences of 10 teachers who will integrate non-formal methods and ICT tools in the didactic activity with adults; Increase of the percentage by 20% of the graduates from the evening education who obtain the professional certificate and the decrease of the number of absences by 20%; Improving the English language skills of the teachers who will develop a bilingual methodological guide; Maintaining the number of students, by continuing the partnership and setting up a class within the "Second Chance" Program.

Management details: Approved budget 26010 EURO. Time 16 months (1 October 2020 – 31 January 2022).

Activities approved: The teachers participate at the following courses: Dual education and work-based learning; Project Based Learning; Introduction to the Finnish Education Model

Results: Pedagogical competences for applying in adult education some non-formal methods (student-centered, practice-based or project-based); Computer skills and language use of online tools for international collaboration; Social skills of cooperation and exchange of good practices with individuals and organizations working in the field of education; A "Methodological guide for the use of non-formal methods" which will influence the activity of many teachers in the county.

Conclusions: The project increases the visibility of our school at national and international level, its prestige, the confidence of the partner schools in the capacity of the high school of professional training and will ensure the achievement of the objective of maintaining the numbers of students.

Keywords: Education, Grants, Projects

**BUILDING SCHOOL-WIDE INCLUSIVE, POSITIVE AND EQUITABLE
LEARNING
ENVIRONMENTS THROUGH A SYSTEMS-CHANGE APPROACH [SWPBS]
[SWPBS-SCHOOL-WIDE POSITIVE BEHAVIOR SUPPORTS]**

(1) Loredana OLTEANU

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Project type: Erasmus+ KA3 Project, Support for Policy Reform, Ref. no.: 606687-EPP-1-2018-2-CY-EPPKA3-PI-POLICY

Promoter /Coordinator: Centre for the Advancement of Research & Development in Educational Technology Limited (CARDET), Cyprus

Local coordinator for the University of Pitești: Assoc. Professor Dr. Eng. Dumitru CHIRLEȘAN

Partners: Centre for the Advancement of Research and Development in Educational Technology

(CARDET), Cyprus (coordinator); Paidagogiko Instituto Kyprou, Ministry of Education, Cyprus; Innovade Ltd, Cyprus; Jyvaskeylan Yliopisto, Finland; Kontiolahden kunta, Finland; City of Varkaus, Finland; Lappeenranta Kaupunki, Finland; Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis, Greece; Periferiaki Dieftihisi Protovathmias Kai Defterovathmias Ekpaidefsis, Greece; University of Pitesti, Romania; Arges County School Inspectorate, Romania.

Objectives: The purpose of this project is to implement SWPBS across four countries. SWPBS aims to develop a positive learning environment in our classrooms, to establish an inclusive non-discriminatory social culture and necessary socio-emotional and behavioural supports for all students in a school. Develop external training capacity at public authority levels to support schools in implementing SWPBS levels. Increase internal training capacity among school staff and other professionals in SWPBS practices. Development of quality resources for the implementation of SWPBS.

Total project grant: 2.265.916 Euro/ Total expenditure (grant) for the University of Pitești: 141.896 Euro

Duration: two years (2019-2020/2020-2021)

Activities: Teacher’s training. All students are trained using a common language and pursuing the same end goals- an effective discipline involves the development of confidence in the student's own forces, the development of self-control and self-discipline.

Results: 4 training courses were offered for the teaching staff of the school and 5 trainings for the school coordination team. Lesson projects applied in 23 classes. Over 575 students participated in activities designed for them. Digital resources/ educational support materials necessary for the implementation of SWPBS (tier 1) were produced.

Keywords: Education, Projects, Erasmus

PLAN YOUR CAREER, PLAN YOUR FUTURE

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(2) Karine NAPOL

(1) “Maria Teiuleanu” Economical College, Pitești, Romania

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Title of the project: PLAN YOUR CAREER, PLAN YOUR FUTURE

Coordinator of the project: Lycée Général et Technologique de Bellevue, French Martinique

Source of the grant: Erasmus +Programme, KA2 Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices, Strategic Partnerships

Partners: Colegiul Economic “Maria Teiuleanu”-Romania, IGS Busecker Tal- Germany, Ave Maria La Quinta-Spain, Kemalpaşa Ferizent Bulum Anadolu Lisesi-Turkey.

Objectives: developing the entrepreneurial skills and adaptability of students to the labour market at local, national and European level; providing equal opportunities for young people in education and on the labour market; promoting active citizenship and social inclusion for all young people; reducing youth unemployment by facilitating the school-labour market transition;

Management details: total amount 141.680 euro, duration 24 months (2018-2020);

Activities approved: student exchanges, non formal activities, setting up training firms, interviewing successful entrepreneurs

Results:150 students in student exchanges, 35 teachers, 60 parents, 30 representatives of economic agents, 100 graduates involved, 5 training firms, 5 Erasmus + corners, 1 common website of the project (www.planyourcareer.eu), 5 contact lists of entrepreneurs from the partner countries, 5 presentations / seminars on topics of European interest

Conclusions: The project consisted in the exchange of good practices in the field of entrepreneurship, developed the entrepreneurial spirit of the students involved, offered various opportunities through direct contact with labour market representatives. It aligned students with the concept of lifelong learning and flexible career options, reducing segmentation in the labour market, developing communication and writing skills in English, cultural interaction of pupils and teachers from five partner countries, providing a unique opportunity for students to acquire knowledge and a deep understanding of the diversity of the European community.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Career, Projects.

INTRODUCTION TO EUROPEAN SOLIDARITY CORPS PROGRAMME

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ESC Program Goals: Increasing inter-communal solidarity through voluntary activities; Promoting solidarity as a value; To increase the participation of young people and organizations in accessible and high-quality solidarity activities; Promote social inclusion; Providing work experience to young people in different countries.

- 1) **Individual Volunteering:** Can last from 2 months up to 12 months; Is full-time (between 30 and 38 hours a week); Allows you to contribute to the daily work of an organisation that is actively benefiting the local community; Is usually 'cross-border' – i.e. in a different country to where you live; In some cases, you can take part for a shorter time (from 2 weeks to 2 months) – for example for participants with fewer opportunities, or disabilities.
- 2) **Team Volunteering:** Can last between 2 weeks and 2 months; Is full-time (between 30 and 38 hours a week); You volunteer with people from at least 2 different countries; The group will be between 10 and 40 volunteers and include people with fewer opportunities; Is usually abroad, though it can be in your home country.

Supporting organisation: based in your home country, will help you prepare for your experience abroad (it used to be called 'sending organisation').

Host organisation: will receive and help you in your destination country.

What is a Solidarity Project: The challenges in your neighbourhood and the causes that matter to you. Project should be devoted to these types of challenge, but it can also help tackle regional or even national issues. Should demonstrate 'European value' – drawing on priorities identified by the EU, and it can last from 2 to 12 months.

Section A

Psychology and development

Session 1

Professionals in personal development

Moderator: Mihaela Lungu

THE NEED FOR COUNSELLING FOR PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLSTUDENTS DURING THE PANDEMIC OF SARSCOV2 VIRUS

- (1) Mihaela LUNGU,
- (2) PhD. Emilia Rodica CIUCĂ,
- (3) Albert VAMANU

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- (2) Head Master of the Argeş, County Centre for Educational Resources and Assistance, Piteşti, Romania
- (3) Research Representative, COVID-19: Supporting Parents, Adolescents, and Children during Epidemics (Co-SPACE); The Oxford Psychological Interventions for Children and adolescents (TOPIC) Research Group, Department of Experimental Psychology, University of Oxford

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Objective: The research was meant as a primary analysis regarding the perception of school counselling needs among students, during the first wave of the pandemic in Romania.

Material and methods: A specific 10 items questionnaire was developed to explore the need for counselling services of the primary and secondary school population of Argeş county. The research was developed by the County Centre for Educational Resources and Assistance, and data were collected during May and June 2020, through google forms. The questionnaire was presented as a self-applied short test in order to find if you need to look for a school counsellor. The pupils were getting a fast answer: any score of 2 or more (out of 10) indicates a counselling session could be useful.

Results: There were no scores higher than 8. Most of the respondents, 73.39% (N=575) reported scores equal or higher than 2. Item 4 registered the most alarming answer, 69% of pupils reported they lose awareness of time when playing on computer or mobile phone. Regarding unusual feelings in the body, 45% reported noticing them. Also 39.5% said that they find it hard to fall asleep though they feel very tired, and 37.7% answered that they feel an internal tension, an unspecific fear.

Conclusions:

During the pandemic the counselling need felt by primary and secondary school pupils was high (over 70% of the respondents). Anxiety and depression symptoms were experienced by the participants in high rate (over 30%, even over 50 %). Social and communication skills show low levels. Using gadgets (phone, computer, tablet etc.) affected other investigated symptoms by increasing them

Limits: respondents were pupils from middle to high economic level, that had access to technology during the pandemic. They were also the pupils whose parents/ tutors did not feel the effects of the changes in the working market that much, a better social distribution of the collection would most probably lead to different results.

Keywords: school counselling, pandemic, pupils

MANAGING PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT: AN EMERGING STRATEGY FOR BUILDING LEADERSHIP CAPACITY

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Objectives: This paper aims at a conceptual delimitation of the personal development in the educational environment, with emphasis on identifying strategies and techniques to facilitate the manager's own personal development process, mapping his professional skills, personal and leadership competencies, seen as a trigger of effective development in the organization.

Materials and methods: The methodology consisted of literature review and documentation. School organizations from Romania are faced with the continuous perspective of change both in the legislative and in the curricular plan, but also at the social level.

Results: We established a correlation between the manager's personal development process, transposed into management strategies and its implications in the development of the organization.

Conclusions: Personal development is a key strategy for an effective and inspirational leadership.

Keywords: communication, leadership, management

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATION IN PREVENTION AND COMBATING ORGANISATIONAL CONFLICTS

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Objectives: The main objective of this paper is to draw attention to the importance of the communication in the organizational environment. We considered studying communication as, within any organization, communication is an essential process through which the exchange of messages and information takes place in order to achieve the planned purpose and objectives.

Materials and methods: As this is a theoretical paper, we chose specialty literature analyzing to extract the most important aspects of communication in organizational environments, underlying the need for assertive communication.

Results: A theoretical knowledge of communicational levels increases organizational performance. It is of the utmost importance to understand the importance of assertiveness in the communication process, with emphasis on the organizational environment.

Conclusions: In the process of improving communication-related performance, one of the important skills of the manager is to receive accurate and correct feedback regarding the impact of one's own message on others. This requires sensitivity, as most people feel a certain fear in the face of direct confrontation with someone who asks them about their performance.

Keywords: communication, conflict, school organization.

A HOLISTIC APPROACH OF THE PATIENT WITH ONCOLOGICAL PATHOLOGIES

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Objectives: Holism is the idea that various systems should be seen as a whole, not just as separate parts. The holistic approach of patients diagnosed with oncology involves the integral approach of man as a bio-psycho-social being, not only determining the diagnosis but also the causes of the problem. Holistic thinking towards patients means thinking about each patient as an individual, with their own medical history, desires, values, social circumstances, all of which have a role in their health. The combination of holistic healthcare and contemporary medicine expands a nurse's ability to provide the most effective treatment options for each patient. To successfully treat patients, nurses must possess the necessary skills, abilities about care, and understand the physical and emotional influences that disease can have on a person.

Materials and methods: The method of the interview and the case study to establish the relationship and the degree of interaction of the nurse with the patient. 46 patients, 23 men and 23 women were interviewed to assess the degree of interaction. 78% are dissatisfied with attitude and individual care and 22% are satisfied with behavior, communication and care provided.

Results: This study constructively analyzes some hypotheses underlying the focus on the cancer patient and suggests that an individual approach to care focused on relationships, attitude, empathy is needed.

Conclusion: For an effective holistic approach, the time given to the patient is important, which is often limited due to the increased number of patients. For this reason, the nurse must spend quality time in order to discover the psychological and social needs of the patient and help him to meet them. Thus, the goal of nurses is to help patients diagnosed with oncology to go through easily to deal with certain problems they face. Currently, there is a considerable emphasis on promoting holistic approaches that have become a watchword for good practice.

Key-words: holism, holistic theories, holistic medicine, holistic approach, nurse, patient cancer, oncology.

CLINICAL HYPNOSIS

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Objective: The main objective of studying clinical hypnosis is to demystify clinical hypnosis and demonstrate that its efficiency was scientifically proven.

Materials and methods: Qualitative literature analysis was used to touch the objective.

Results: Specialty literature analyzed is mainly proving that scientific research was performed in the field of clinical hypnosis to provide a clearer view on its benefits and to check on risks (if any) in a controlled environment.

Conclusions: Clinical hypnosis can be used by professionals in both clinical and non-clinical environments as a powerful tool (as it is scientifically proven) for managing different forms of mental or somatic disorders such as: cancer (increasing the quality of life for terminally ill patients, pain relieving, boosting the immunity system of the patient to help him/her get healthy), depression, all sorts of phobias, raising self esteem and many more health issues may be successfully addressed.

Keywords: clinical hypnosis, relaxation, breathing.

SCHOOL COUNSELLING A POWERFUL TOOL FOR CHANGING A CHILD'S LIFE

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Objective: The paper offers the results of a primary analysis regarding the perception of school counselling among students, parents and teachers in Romania.

Material and methods. Based on non-specific research developed by the County Centre for Educational Resources and Assistance, data were collected during May and June 2020, through google forms questionnaires separated for students (primary and secondary school), parents and teachers.

Results. Less than 5% of pupils reported asking for school counselling (N=1003) and over 16% appreciated the counselling intervention as very useful. Over 50% of parents (N=531) reported participating in group counselling sessions in school and 54% appreciated as extremely useful, while only 26.6% reported asking for individual counselling in school and 48.6% appreciated as very useful. Most of the teachers 94.5% (N=458) reported collaborating with school counsellor in class and 89.7% appreciated as very useful. Almost none of the parents could report a topic from the counselling sessions, very few of the pupils could remember one, but most of the teachers reported specific topics exactly. Parents appreciation regarding school counselling services tends to go around extreme values, as if the support was either extremely good or no good at all.

Conclusions. Counselling services are more appreciated by the educational experts, and at some extent by the primary beneficiary: pupils. Parents might appreciate it through the personal need of comfort (social or psychological). Extending data collection to several counties and deepen the quality of data, with information like topics reached during counselling sessions.

Limits: to students in Argeș county, that had access to technology during the collection time

Keywords: school counselling, parents' perception, pandemic

Session 2

Psychological development through education

Moderator: Cristina Ipate-Toma

SOMATIZATION OF EMOTIONS IN CHILDREN

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Objectives: Somatization is the way in which internal conflicts are physically manifested by various conditions: headache, stomach, throat or ear pain, nausea, vomiting, soft stools, the need to urinate, cough or shortness of breath, palpitations, fever, exhaustion.

Results: In order to be understood, the symptoms must be placed in a socio-familial context. When you are aware of the events in the child's life, you can more easily realize the things that could have disturbed his balance. The results are: a better understanding by parents and teachers of children's needs.

Conclusions: Going to kindergarten or school can sometimes be a fear-causing experience that the child cannot control: fear of abandonment, fear of getting lost, fear of the unknown.

The quarrels, prohibitions and limits that are brutally imposed on him, can awaken in him the fear of not losing the love of his parents, feelings of guilt or anger.

Key words: somatic, symptoms, feelings.

STUDENT PORTRAIT WITH SLD – CASE STUDY

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Objectives: Through this work we aim to present a case studio that has as objectives: Integration of a student with specific learning disorders/ ESL in mainstream education. Supporting the student with Specific Learning Disorders in achieving school success.

Materials and methods: Counseling the student with Specific Learning Disorders, Counseling the student's Parents with Specific Learning Disorders, Counseling teachers, Counseling the student's students-colleagues with IST.

Results: She is currently a student in the ninth grade at the high school. He entered the special places given to students with SLD, (if it was not for this opportunity, he would not have reached this class). Every morning she is smiling, she is satisfied with what she has. He managed to read 1-2 books. The first book she read was Like the Fish in the Tree, by Lynda Mullaly Hunt.

Conclusions: In order for a child with SLD (or any child with difficulties) it is important to work in a team. Let this team be formed as early as the third grade for dyslexia, and at the latest the fourth grade for dyscalculia. The team must include the teacher, the parents, other teachers of the class, the fellow students and the teacher school counselor to coordinate the entire activity. Early signs to work on them starting with the pre-abecedary elements)

Keywords: SLD (Specific Learning Disorders, dyscalculia, dyslexia, counseling)

PRETEENS WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS AND AGGRESSIVE POTENTIAL SHOW DISTORTED SELF-ESTEEM

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Objective: The general objective of this paper is showing that preteens with special educational needs who have aggressive potential show distorted self-esteem, either too high or too low values.

Materials and methods: The investigative approach was carried out in 2018 and includes three case studies of three preadolescents, aged between 14-15 years, who committed various crimes - physical and verbal aggression, theft. All have mild mental deficiency (grade I).

Results: The analyse shows that, regardless of whether they were over- or underestimated, the investigated subjects really have an unrealistic self-esteem that causes them to act dysfunctional.

Conclusions: However, it seems that these evaluation deficiencies are not so much due to the aggressive potential, but rather to the mental deficiency that prevents the realization of information processing, evaluations and correct and functional decisions. Also, the case studies showed that these distortions in self-perception and self-evaluation are also the consequence of educational deficiencies, of the negative evaluations that the subjects received in childhood from the family. Intervention programs should be created and developed both in increasing self-esteem and in stopping delinquent behaviors, specific to the particularities of each subject.

Keywords: special educational needs.

WORKING IN MULTIDISCIPLINARY TEAMS

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Objectives. The aim of this paper is to present the basics of a multidisciplinary team.

Material and methods. The present study examines the concept, key factors, core competencies, benefits, challenges and issues of working in a multidisciplinary team. We also used qualitative literature review.

Results indicate multiple advantages for mental health professionals working together in a multidisciplinary team, also the challenges.

Conclusions. The multidisciplinary teams in mental health services are constantly improving their efficacy based on the research, as an evolving process.

Keywords: multidisciplinary team (MDT), therapist, competencies.

PLEADING FOR A PROPER AND COHERENT EDUCATION

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Objectives: Nowadays it is increasingly talked about the usage of a democratic relations system, based on a change of attitude towards the pupil and on the flexibility between educational actors. One of the most important requirements of growing the educational performance with pupils is represented by assuring unity of actions regarding all the educational factors: school, pupils and parents. The statement that school is the one that tremendously establishes the development of human personality implies also that a coherent education must conjoint the role of the family.

One of the main objectives, in order to prepare teachers properly, is the knowing of pupils and their groups and this purpose can be accomplished just through close cooperation between school and family. A constant focus that the teacher must follow during the parent's meetings is to identify the difficulties they encounter in the relationships with their children, as well as to present methods of improving the communication.

Results: School and family are two main institutions that go hand in hand and they can be perceived as interdependence networks that shape a set of social relations. The concepts of “failure” and “success” are meant to be understood as the results of a smaller or larger contradiction or degree of dissonance/consonance regarding the types of social relations that characterize the two interdependence networks.

Conclusion: Therefore, the partnership between school and family is well-founded. Each actor involved in the education act increases the child’s chances of success with full marks both on a scholar and personal level.

Key words: partnership, democratic relations, attitude.

RESEARCH - SCHOOL VIOLENCE AND ITS CAUSES

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Objectives: We conducted this research in order to develop and implement activities/projects/strategies in order to prevent/improve/reduce school violence. We considered that it is necessary to take into account the factors that can determine an aggressive/violent behavior of the student, when we want intervention in the field of school violence.

Results: From the research undertaken we found that one of the most important factors that can cause school violence is the family environment from which the violent student comes.

Raised in a conflicted, tense, unstable family environment, or in which parents do not know or fail to establish a harmonious relationship with the child, he can exhibit aggressive behavior both in school and outside it.

Methods and materials: Given this fact, strategies for the prevention and reduction of violence in the school should include aspects that involve parents in various programs and projects, through which to train, to develop parenting skills.

Conclusion: Given that the family is a determining factor in the school violence of a student, as an alternative in his emotional stability remains the school and it is necessary to assist the family and include it in parental counseling programs to combat student violence.

Keywords: violence, causes, school

Section B

Development and education

Session 1

Management of educational institutions and groups – PPS

Moderator: Camelia Ioanăș

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF CONFLICTS IN SCHOOL ORGANISATIONS

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Objectives: In the school environment there are a variety of specific conflicts derived from the particularities of educational activities (teaching-learning and training) and tensions or dysfunctions that occur in the process of interaction between curriculum elements - objectives, content / knowledge, teaching technology (assessment and grading in relationships teacher-student, school-parents, school-institutions).

Results: Conflicts can have both positive and negative results in the school. If a school organization achieves the ideal of "no conflict" it is probably in difficulty. Conflict is a sign of an active, solid, "going" school organization. Conflicts become a problem when they become too many, in which case they lead to a loss of human and material resources. Moderate conflicts must be encouraged, but they must not get out of control.

Conclusion: Too many or too few conflicts should be avoided. The ideal strategy for conflicts is to keep them in an intermediate zone.

Keywords: conflict management, school organization, communication

CONFLICT IN THE DYNAMICS OF THE SCHOOL ORGANISATION

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Objectives: Conflict, as a form of interaction between beings, is present in the whole organization of the living world, but humans are the only beings on earth who come into conflict with each other and for reasons other than those related to survival. The school, as a subsystem of the social system cannot avoid conflicts. The objective is to diminish conflicts between all school participants (students, teachers and parents).

Materials and methods: games that help teachers and students solve conflicts.

Results: In school, conflicts are present both within the various categories of human resources that make up the school organization (students, teachers, auxiliary teachers, administrative staff), and between these groups, between school and family, between school and local community.

Conclusion: The teacher has a decisive role in resolving these conflicts. He must be a peacemaker who uses, however, constructively the conflict in order to achieve the established educational goals.

Keywords: Conflict, school organization, communication

MANAGERIAL STRATEGIES FOR PREVENTING, REDUCING, COMBATING AND RESOLVING CONFLICTS IN SCHOOL INSTITUTIONS

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Objectives: The ability to successfully manage conflicts is an important skill for school managers, closely related to personal development. The "appropriate" management strategy in a given situation requires identifying the origin of the conflict, the participants, and their relationships, in order to apply the most effective resolution technique. Since conflict is inevitable in schools, school managers must be prepared to respond to them, not necessarily to eliminate them, because it is impossible, but to find optimal ways to resolve them.

Methods and materials: The appropriate management strategy in a given situation requires identifying the origin of the conflict, the participants, and their relationships, in order to apply the most effective resolution technique. Anticipation, conflict identification must be the first two phases of effective conflict management.

Results: The leaders of the school organization must identify if the conflict situations are fundamental or emotional, personalized. Fundamental conflict situations refer to decisions, directions and actions, while the second category is personality conflicts. By identifying and understanding the nature of the conflict, previously identified conflict resolution strategies can be effectively addressed.

Conclusion: Effective management of conflict situations requires reducing the autocratic character of school management and transforming the school principal into a democratic leader concerned with establishing interpersonal relationships in the organization, communication and collaboration, motivating teachers to achieve goals and increase responsibility in solving tasks. The process of conducting a qualitative analysis of the opinion of teachers and school managers on conflict situations can be continued by centralizing and monitoring information on how to resolve conflict situations, by evaluating and disseminating "good practices".

Keywords: conflict resolution, school organization, personal development, school management.

EDUCATING NURSES TO PREVENT PRESSURE ULCERS

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Objectives: To evaluate the effects of educational interventions for health care nurses on pressure ulcer prevention. Education of healthcare staff has been recognized as an integral component of pressure ulcer prevention. These educational programmes are directed towards influencing behaviour change on the part of the healthcare professional, to encourage preventative practices with the aim of reducing the incidence of pressure ulcer development.

Materials and methods: The use of didactic films, case studies, observation sheets in the teaching-learning process plays an important role in the training of nurses.

Results: We reviewed the evidence on the effect of health care nurse education on pressure ulcer prevention. We explored all types of education, regardless of how it was delivered, as long as it focused on pressure ulcer prevention. Healthcare personnel working in pressure ulcer prevention in any professional setting. Settings in which care was delivered included inpatient and outpatient wards, community clinics, patient homes.

Conclusion: Does educating health care nurses about pressure ulcer prevention make any difference to the incidence of pressure ulcers or nurses' knowledge of pressure ulcer prevention. This is because the included studies provided evidence of very low safety. Therefore, further information is needed to clarify the impact of health care nurse education on pressure ulcer prevention.

Keywords: educational programmes, ulcers, educational interventions, observation sheets prevention, case studies, patient.

TEACHING COMMUNICATION OF BAD NEWS IN MEDICAL SCHOOL

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Objective: Delivering bad news is a very common in medical daily practice. Several studies have shown a lack of effective communication skills amongst medical students, particularly concerning how to deliver bad news. The SPIKES protocol allows communicating bad news in a 6-step method. The aim of this study is to investigate the perspective of students related to this subject.

Material and methods: A 45-minute lecture "Breaking Bad News" was taught to 160 fourth-year students from the medical school in Chisinau city using the SPIKES training protocol. After the lecture, all students were given an online survey. After the analysis of the data extracted from the survey the following were found.

Results: Fifty-four students answered the online survey. Eighty three percent said that the theme should have an important role in their further daily medical practice, and most of students rated the physicians' role as challenging. Sixty percent of students expressed that communicating bad news was an integral part of the medical course curriculum. Regarding the SPIKES' protocol, 48% felt that the first step would be the easiest to put in practice, and 40% felt that the fifth step related to "Emotions" would be the most difficult.

Discussion: In general, the students would like to gain competencies in communicating bad news using a practical approach

Conclusions: Students highly valued theoretical and practical approaches in teaching the communication of bad news. Therefore, we encourage a combination approach in pre-graduate medical education.

Keywords: Communication; Education; Students, Medical; SPIKES; Breaking Bad News.

THE POWER OF ASKING QUESTIONS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Objectives: The purpose of this paper is to offer the audience a short and useful 4 steps method to be used by teachers to help pupils/students become confident in asking questions in schools. The objectives are: handing an easy-to-use instrument for teachers; enhancing participation and involvement in pupils/students; increasing creativity; raising class cohesion; decreasing the stigma of vulnerability for asking questions.

Results: The proposed results will be increasing participation in classes and curiosity for children of all ages and also handing a better class management tool for teachers.

Conclusion: Asking questions is an early life skill that tends to be forgotten with age, a skill so important that it can actually lead to innovation (please refer to cases presented in the article). Encouraging children to ask questions is actually helping reducing bullying in schools and it is also reducing the stigma of not being an “expert”. Openness to receiving questions from pupils/students means also a paradigm shift for teachers, as instead of answers/fixed knowledge, they are opening up to new and perhaps interesting perspectives.

Keywords: questions, answers, innovation.

Session 2

Innovative and online teaching

Moderator: Ana-Maria Badea

VALIDATION OF THE PEDAGOGICAL AUTHORITY IN THE CONTEXT OF ONLINE TEACHING

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Objective: Between the deontological and the epistemic dimension of the pedagogical authority there is a close interdependence, these being two vectors which, by assembly, are enriched with a new property, respectively the direction.

Materials and methods: The use of multimedia tools in the teaching-learning process is a challenge for many of the teachers, this also having an impact on their pedagogical authority.

Results: This challenge has become more relevant in the context in which online teaching has become a necessity, not just an option. Students are encouraged to develop skills and to improve their online usage in order to continue their education.

Conclusion: The professional and, implicitly, the personal development of the teachers have turned out to be a requirement so as to maintain their pedagogical authority viable. In order to be efficient, teachers have to master both digital and methodological components so that the integration of new technologies in the process should be permanently correlated with the goals, objectives and purposes of education.

Key words: pedagogical authority, online teaching, development, technology, methodology

INTERACTIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES - LEVERS IN THE FORMATION OF GEOGRAPHY-SPECIFIC COMPETENCIES

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Objectives: Nowadays, when the need for training and development of intellectual abilities, skills, abilities, aptitudes, feelings and emotions of high school students is increasingly acute, a useful way through which the teacher helps students in the process of teaching - authentic learning, training of geography-specific competencies is given by interactive teaching strategies.

Materials and methods: the educational act is designed so that the emphasis is on active learning, the student and not the teacher, he must give up old rigid practices and embrace innovative and interactive teaching strategies aimed at training geography-specific skills. Interactivity also involves competition on the one hand, and cooperation on the other. The two aspects sometimes interact in various learning situations, and in the situation of a student-centred educational process, the teacher accompanies the student to knowledge and becomes a co-participant in school and extracurricular activities.

Results: Teaching strategies are those that establish how the content is customized to facilitate learning by the student, and the teacher must achieve for the formation of geographical skills the best forms of organization that have advantages and disadvantages. Starting from the design and implementation of educational activities based on interactive teaching strategies, students are given the opportunity to get involved in the process of their own training, to express their ideas, opinions and to develop skills specific to geography, so it becomes active, motivated to engage in numerous activities to develop skills.

Conclusion: The first part of the paper defines the concept of interactive teaching strategy according to several authors, and the second part expresses the components of a teaching strategy.

Key words: active learning, geography, interactive.

SWOT ANALYSIS OF MATHEMATICAL CLASSES DURING ONLINE TEACHING

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Objectives: Living with students during this pandemic period, I made from my own experience an analysis of the development of math classes. At the same time, I involved a student in this endeavor, whose opinions can be found in the article.

Materials and methods: I preferred to make these observations in terms of a SWOT analysis, highlighting the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of this period. In the mirror are also the opinions of a student.

Results: Without claiming a large scale, I think I managed to point out some aspects relevant to this period, both in terms of the discipline taught and the emotional impact on all involved: students, teachers, parents.

Conclusions: Although this period was full of multiple opportunities for career development, I think it should be used especially as a landmark to enhance the simple joys we can live together at school.

Keywords: School - place of hope.

SCHOOL COUNSELOR'S DOCUMENTS – EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES FOR THE FUTURE

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- (3) Mihaela Lungu,
- (4) Camelia Ioanas,
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Objectives: Improving the quality of the work results in school counselors' activity; increased efficiency in activity monitoring.

Materials and methods: The school counselors' activities and needs survey was an integrated part in a wider study regarding previous activity of the counselors; we also chose the documentation method in order to supplement the documents volume as a base for developing a new portfolio. The documentation focused on actual and possible instruments that are useful for increasing the quality of school counseling activity.

Results: The portfolio of school counselors from Arges County is a collection of 34 documents, resulted from the survey and documentation activities.

Conclusion: The portfolio is the instrument through which the school counselors have a broader control over his/her activity in school, thus improving the efficiency of his/her activity and making sure the activity is done in a more organized manner. The new counselors will have a clear image of the content of the portfolio. The senior counselors will have a refresh of their lists in order to make sure that they owe the right documents in their portfolio.

Key words: portfolio, school counselor, organizing.

PROVIDING THE APPROPRIATE RIGHTS TO CHILDREN WITH SEN

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Objective: Informing parents about the benefits of attending special kindergarten courses, preparation of beneficiaries' files, correct implementation of legislation

Methods and materials: National Education Law no. 1/2011; H.G. 564/2017 on the manner of granting the rights of children with special educational needs enrolled in the pre-university education system.

Results and conclusions: Attendance of courses by all children enrolled in the unit; The progress of children with SEN so that some of them will attend mainstream education courses. The children from SFÂNTA ELENA Special Kindergarten are children with special educational needs and are enrolled based on the school / professional orientation certificate issued by the School / Professional Orientation Commission within the Argeș Educational Resources and Assistance Center.

They benefit from specialized programs in the educational and recovery instructional process, depending on the bio-psycho-emotional particularities of each one.

In addition to the specialized educational act, they benefit from certain monetary rights (daily allowance for food and allowance for school supplies, barracks, clothing and footwear), regulated by the National Education Law and H.G. 564/2017.

Based on these normative acts, the procedure for granting the rights of children with SEN enrolled in kindergarten was drawn up.

Session 3

Educational psychology

Moderator: Mihaela Lungu

THE IMPACT OF GRADES ON STUDENTS

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Objective: since the assessment is an essential element of the teaching process, we have set out the goal to have a study about the impact of grades on students.

Materials and methods: a questionnaire have been submitted to a number of students from two high schools in our town. It contained multiple choice questions. After analyzing the answers and making diagrams, they were interpreted.

Results: after analyzing the individual answers, there have been shown aspects of the relation teacher-student, the class environment, and teacher's attitude. Aspects related to student initiative, teachers' reaction to good/bad answers from students, the effect of these on the students have also been noted. The impact of grades upon students' self- esteem and also on parent-child relation has been highlighted.

Conclusion: the given answers, after having been analyzed, offer the general image of the Romanian high school system as it is outlined in the results at the national exams.

Keywords: education, grades, study

DEVELOPMENT OF THE AXIOLOGICAL FRAME OF REFERENCE OF THE YOUNG STUDENT THROUGH SELF-EDUCATION

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The purpose of the research is to determine the theoretical landmarks on the axiological reference of primary school students and the development of the Self-Education Training Program of the axiological reference of young students in the perspective of resolving / preventing school conflicts of intra- and interpersonal nature.

Objectives of the investigation:

- Identifying the theoretical foundations of education through and for values;
- Study of the axiological frame of reference of primary school students;
- Determining the vulnerabilities of young students in the area of school conflicts and the levels of acquisition of general-human values of students;
- Establishing the degree of preparation of teachers for axiological education;

Materials and methods: In the research at the finding stage, a questionnaire was applied through which we aimed to collect relevant information on axiological education, and identify teachers' perceptions of the formation of axiological reference in students who could anticipate school conflicts.

Results: The formation of axiological competence in young students implies their ability to discover new connections in value systems.

Conclusions: The theoretical research of the complex issue of constellation / taxonomy of values and axiological education has led to the identification of relevant meanings of concepts, principles and factors that stimulate the cultivation of general human values of young students.

Keywords: axiological education, self-education, school conflicts.

THE INVOLVEMENT OF THE FAMILY IN SCHOOL LIFE AS A STRATEGY OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

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Objectives: The concept of partnership between school and community relies on the principle of complementarities of services provided by organizations working in the community. Schools are strongly anchored in the local community and through their status, through the competences of human resources involved in the educational system; they can become the promoter of the community partnership. The student's family makes the connection between the educational service provider and the community. Those children who are supported by their parents, who have adequate pro-school attitudes in the family, achieve high school performance and have a high degree of aspiration compared to the level of schooling they want to reach. A communion is formed around the children, which can function as a positive coalition of educational and cultural support.

Conclusion: Educational partnerships are an essential component in organizing and conducting collaboration with the entire community, so that it benefits from members - conscious, educated and responsible citizens.

Key words: education, school-family partnership, local community

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SCHOOL MOTIVATION AND PERSONAL AUTONOMY IN ADOLESCENTS

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Objective: The general objective of this work was to inventory the relationship between school motivation and personal autonomy in adolescents.

Material and methods: Personal Autonomy questionnaire. School motivation questionnaire. The research was built on a test-retest design. A training program focused on the development of personal autonomy and motivation of adolescents was developed.

Results: The role of motivation in education is very complex. The training program brings more significant improvements to personal autonomy than school motivation.

Conclusions: The research concluded that there is a direct correlation between school motivation and personal autonomy. Moreover, personal autonomy and school motivation are gender conditioned. I believe that intervention programs should be created and developed both in increasing self-esteem, autonomy and school motivation.

Keywords: motivation, personal autonomy

PRACTICAL APPLICATION OF STUDENT'S SKILLS AND INTERESTS THROUGH EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

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Objective: The purpose of this paper is to inform the public opinion and interested authorities about the beneficial effects of the school celebration, as an extracurricular activity in optimizing the student-teacher-parent relationship.

The fundamental condition for training, developing and forming the student's personality, is to attend the school and the extracurricular activities. Practice has proved the importance of combining the two types rather than comparing them. We consider that the participation at this conference is a good opportunity to value the beneficial effects of the school show, as extracurricular activity in improving the student-teacher-parent relationship. Starting from a real example of pedagogical approach: Mother's Day school show we will provide details on how this experience has been felt as a "celebration" both by the children, but also by the teachers and especially by the parents. When we projected the scenario of our school show we took into consideration the students needs, their ages and their psychological particularities so that the artistic material to be able to have artistic and educational value.

Materials and methods: didactic activity of the participating teachers, celebration as extracurricular activity, involvement of parents in the school-student-parent relationship.

Results: 21 students, their parents and relatives, participating teachers, social worker, principal participated in the celebration your birthday, mommy, having as teacher responsible for activity the psycho educational teacher R.C. at the school Inclusive Education Centre Saint Stelian, Costesti.

Conclusions: The project was a success, at the end of the activity a positive attitude was surprised, the objectives were achieved. the school-family relationship has been transformed into a reality of openness, full of tolerance, empathy, and cohesion. A real and successful partnership is expected between our school-students-parents of students

Keywords: education, extracurricular activity, school celebration, personal development

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